

Impact of Gender Equality on Social Development

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Abstract

Social development is the process of improving the well-being of every individual in society. Several problems of social development in the UK were on the rise such as unemployment, racism issues, and depression and anxiety which are badly affecting social development. For achieving the sustainable goal the gender of each country has to equally participate in the social development of the country. This study's main aim is to highlight whether social development is possible without gender equality. The main objective of the study is to identify the importance of Gender Equality for social development. The current research has adopted a qualitative research design under which the method has been associated with an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon. The use of qualitative design has led to the use of an inductive approach which allowed the researcher to further generalize the findings from general to specific. The researcher collected information by using secondary sources. Promotion of gender equality through targeted programs and policies can imply economic growth and gender equality simultaneously. This in return can improve the argument for public investment across gender equality. The importance of tradition and culture and the need for engaging with direct and cultural norms support the human right for the attainment of positive transformation across gender equality. With regards to social development gender inequality is considered to be increasingly harmful. The reason is that the quality generally promotes educational outcomes alongside societal health. Therefore, working on the issue of gender is increasingly important as in the UK gender inequality is viewed as one of the most severe inequalities.

Keywords: Cultural norms, Gender Equality, Gender Inequality, Social Development

1. Introduction

As per the widely accepted view, for the evolution and growth of any country, it is important to involve the voice of all individuals in the process of decision-making. The main reason behind this is that all genders are equally ingredients for achieving sustainable growth and development in society. Bühler and Nikitin (2020) believe that various factors are involved in the social development of a country. The primary factors of social development are the improvement of educational status, employment, CSR adoption, and much more. The key term social development can be defined as the process of improving the well-being of every individual in society (Tri, 2020). However, it has been analysed from the research that several problems of social development in the UK were on the rise such as unemployment, racism issues, and depression and anxiety which are badly affecting social development (Ranganathan et al., 2021). The report of Statista, (2021) stated that around a 15.4 % gender pay gap has been found in the UK which is also affecting the development of the country. Furthermore, there is a harassment problem found in the workplace due to which women are less as compared to men which affect social development. The past research also demonstrated that for the social and sustainable development of the globe multiple international communities are paying attention to achieving social development and gender equality because both of them are linked with each other. Sustainablegoals.Org (2022) indicates that gender equality is the condition of the development of a country as it is impossible to socially develop a country without gender equality. Kwon (2017) claimed that in 2016 the Government of 190 countries developed the agenda at the United Nations General Assembly, the 2030 agenda to overcome the problem of social development and mobilise gender equality. The agenda presents that it is impossible to develop the country without gender equality. Worldbank.Org, (2022). For achieving the sustainable goal, the gender of each country has to equally participate in the social development of the country. This study's main aim is to highlight social development without gender equality. The main objective of the study is to identify the importance of Gender Equality for social development. From the previous research, it is seen that there is limited research on social development without gender equality. Therefore, this study is conducted to fulfill the gap in social development without gender equality is impossible. The literature gap for this study is the need for more extensive research in both the literature on industry behaviour and consumer behaviour.

1.1. Aims and objective

The main aim of this study is to shed light on whether social development is possible without gender equality or not. Following are the objective.

- To explore the importance of gender equality for the social development
- To examine whether social development is possible without gender equality or not.
- To provide a recommendation about what measures should be made for social development.

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2. Literature Review

Gender equality is when the gender is provided with equality, opportunities, and responsibilities. Each gender is generally influenced by gender equality be it the men, women, families, or children. The notion tends to influence people across all backgrounds and ages (Girón and Kazemikhasragh, 2022; Ali, 2022). According to Dilli, Carmichael, and Rijpma (2019), gender equality can improve development results, and economic productivity and can undertake good institutions for representatives. Most of the gender disparities continued in the economy. Gender is regarded as one of the notable considerations for development. It is regarded as the way in which the power structure and the social norms influence the opportunities accessible to different groups of women and men. Gender equality is not just a fundamental right of humans but is also an important foundation for a sustainable, prosperous, and peaceful world (Ali, 2022; Bilan et al. 2020; Ali and Naeem, 2017). There has been notable progress in the past few decades. Such that few of the girls tend to be forced into early marriage as more women are serving in the leadership position and the laws are being reformed toward gender equality. However, despite these gains, most of the challenges remain in the economy. The social and discriminatory laws continued to be pervasive as the women are now consistent in political leadership (Dilli, Carmichael, and Rijpma, 2019; Ali, 2015; Ali and Rehman, 2015; Ali, 2018; Ali and Ahmad, 2016; Ali and Audi, 2018; Ali and Bibi, 2017; Ali and Senturk, 2019; Arshad and Ali, 2016; Audi et al., 2022; Audi et al., 2021; Senturk and Ali, 2021).

2.1. Gender and development

Gender equality is significant in its own right while development is the procedure for expanding freedom across all the people. It thereby closes the gap among the genders i.e., males and females as they play part in lowering income and poverty. Gender equality also improves developmental outcomes and economic efficiencies (Pullen Sansfaçon, et al. 2020). In the context of development programmes and the population context, the equality of gender is vital. The reason is that it allows men and women to undertake effective decisions which influence positively over reproductive health. Consequently, empowering women as social, political, and economic actor can modify the choices of policy and make institutions more representative (Pan, Lu, and Zhang, 2021).

2.2. Role of gender in social development

Gender is one of the significant considerations for development. Gender stereotypes influence study choices, behaviour, and attitude regarding the association. It is also revealed by Soleimani et al. (2018), that gender attitudes are a notable transmission mechanism for intergenerational mobility which is beyond wealth and another significant economic factor. Similarly, it is also viewed that the less-restrictive gender norms generally promote a greater labour force. Societies create expectations and norms about gender (Hernandez and Cudiamat, 2018). The gender and the development approach emphasis on the socially constructed differences between women and men. Hence, there is a significant need to challenge the already existing gender relations and roles pertinent to the differences in development (Rai, 2018; Ali, 2022).

2.3. Gender equality impact on social development

Poverty in developed countries is rapidly increasing the main reason behind this is the development gap. Idiho (2020) stated that the positions of men and women are very different in terms of employment, social status, and financial status which is making an immense impact on the social development of the country. Martin (2022) stated that previous research related to gender equality and its impact on social development has been identified. Idiho (2020) stated that in recent times many developing nations are following the gender equality laws in their countries which are helping to improve the overall development of women and the nation. Therefore many countries including China, and the US have made fairness, and justice laws that support gender equality and also help in the process of social development (Idiho, 2020; Girón and Kazemikhasragh, 2022). Gender equality has multiple impacts as it is changing social native and is allowing women and men to work equally which is helping the nation to develop the social status, and the financial status of individuals (Chung et al., 2021). However, to develop the country socially various countries including the UK have started making increments in the access of women in financial systems as the government of several developed countries has developed laws such as the UK government has developed Equality Act 2010 which promotes equal rights and now is also the leading advocate of the inclusion of gender equality in the SDGs which is helping The UK to improve its culture, economy, and infrastructure and also making a positive impact on society (Walkey, Brown and Martin 2022; britishcouncil.org, 2022).

3. Theoretical Framework

Due to Gender equality laws and Act in the UK the gender law and act is helping in boosting the economy of the UK to £518.21 billion and also helping in promoting peace and economic stability due to the contribution made by the genders equally (Consultancy UK, 2019). Apart from this kibbutz developed the Gender equality theory. This theory has immensely supported that gender equality has a positive impact on social development as it helps to improve the work role and employment status which immensely contribute to social development. This theory holds the view about the gender equality among gender (Myers, 2021). Barnett

(2019) believes this theory presents the view that men and women should be treated equally in the sociality because for the development of any nation it is important to promote gender equality. Furthermore, the other theory which is immensely supporting social development in Vygotsky's sociocultural theory. This theory was proposed by Leo Vygotsky. This theory holds the view of presenting the perception of human development, and cultural role in the development of a country and society. However, it is seen that this theory is quite emerging from the aspect of social development because it helps to promote the qualitative change that individuals should bring in their living to improve the way of living and development of society and country (Yurovski, 2021).

4. Research Methodology

Research methodology is regarded as an integral part of the research as it provides a framework that is adopted for achieving the research objectives (Snyder, 2019). The current research has adopted a qualitative research design under which the method has been associated with an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon. The qualitative method has also allowed focusing on the theoretical perspective of the topic which led to a better understanding of the main objectives of the study more comprehensively (Kumar, 2018). The use of qualitative design has led to the use of an inductive approach which allowed the researcher to further generalize the findings from general to specific. In this way, the existing theory was considered which was further generalized in the specific context of the study. The inductive approach has also towards subjectively analysing the overall aim of the study and answering the research questions.

Under the qualitative design, the researcher collected information by using secondary sources. According to Sherif (2018), secondary analysis has the potential implications for qualitative studies that are required to investigate sensitive topics. In this way, the current study is also associated with an important topic related to social development without gender equality. Hence, the use of secondary data was the most essential as it has allowed the collecting of a large amount of information from past studies. However, it was important for the researcher to collect appropriate information which could help in conducting the analysis. For this purpose, the researcher used a specific search strategy where the keywords such as social development and gender equality have been used for searching for the studies. In addition, various databases have been used for collecting information such as Google Scholar, Elsevier, and Taylor and Francis. With the help of these databases, the researcher has collected the studies which were sorted out with the help of inclusion and exclusion criteria. It was ensured that the researchers which were on the topic of social development and gender equality were included and these were conducted between the years 2010 and 2022.

The studies which were on other topics of development such as economic development or cultural development were all excluded. The studies which were not available in English and had subscription issues were also excluded. The selection of the studies led to the identification of common themes. Within these themes, the researcher analysed the information by using content analysis. This analysis technique is used when the data is collected in a qualitative manner and through secondary sources. Hence, the themes for content analysis included the comparison and contrast of the findings from past studies.

5. Findings

5.1. Gender Equality and economic development

Economic growth tends to offer benefits to the population equally. Thus, regardless of the consistent economic growth in the past decades involving low-income countries there still exist notable gender inequalities. These inequalities are not just relevant from the justice and rights point of view but there has been growing attention toward the influence of gender equality on economic growth (Falk and Hermle, 2018). According to Girón and Kazemikhasragh (2022), the promotion of gender equality through targeted programs and policies can imply economic growth and gender equality simultaneously. This in return can improve the argument for public investment across gender equality. The reason is that some private companies largely promote gender equality based on profitability. Moreover, it has been reported by Breda et al. (2022), that lowering specific forms of gender inequality can in return promote the growth of the economy. More particularly, it is viewed that the reduction in the gender gaps particularly in education led to economic pay-off. Therefore, addressing the gender inequalities can in return largely promote economic growth. However, the evidence from the study of Falk and Hermle (2018), displayed how the intervention can improve economic empowerment which has promoted education, income, and subjective wellbeing. Thus, it is significantly viewed that gender inequality tends to result in lower economic growth. Whereas, offering gender equality in the country leads to significant growth for the economy from a positive perspective.

5.2. Gender Equality and its relationship with social development

Community development and gender are a procedure toward sustainable community development which incorporate gender alongside equal involvement and participation. Moreover, it is also viewed that societies having greater equality attain a high level of economic and social rights fulfillment for the member (Alarcón and Cole, 2019). Therefore, enhancing gender equity might be a goal with intrinsic and clear value. However,

it is suggested that gender equity and the attainment of goals including economic and social rights, health, and education are inseparable (Eastin, 2018). Gender equality is regarded as a matter of social justice that enable equal access to resources, rights, and opportunities (Miotto, Polo López, and Rom Rodríguez, 2019). Gender equality also makes society more secure and rich thus in other words the notion of gender equality is critical for the development in terms of security and sustainable peace. Consequently, leadership specifically women's leadership is vital for all levels as it brings change inequality of gender. Therefore, the women leader might not be visible however when the efforts are made they involve practices at the community level. The leader needs to have a clear vision for transforming the country. This is specifically significant in regards to gender issues as the transformation is just possible by engaging with a wide range of stakeholders including men and women. Therefore, it is important to adopt such a method which is key to gender equality (Breda et al. 2020). Another study by Bhattacharya (2022), added that the importance of tradition and culture and the need for engaging with direct and cultural norms support the human right for the attainment of positive transformation across gender equality. Thus, the goals of gender quality can be expressed in the resonating form alongside the local communities.

5.3. Causes of gender inequality in society

Several factors contribute to gender inequality in the context of the UK. For instance, several factors few of the notable factors due to which the UK has not attained gender equality are stereotyping, bias, and other social norms (Zamberlan et al. 2022). It is generally viewed that sex discrimination across the workplace is unlawful in the UK for the past few decades. However, it is regarded as a continuous issue and a serious problem because of potential high-profile claims. For instance, women are considered to be more likely than compare to the man for being subjected to sexual harassment in the workplace (Onaran et al. 2022). According to CIPD (2022), it is indicated that four in ten women tend to experience unwanted sexual behaviour across the workplace. While compared to men more women were treated poorly and they eventually left the job. The gender pay gap in the UK is current 17.3% as the reason includes several societal, cultural, economic, and educational factors. For instance, according to CIPD (2022), the lack of flexible hours of work is one of the potential reasons. Similarly, women are considered to be potential providers of unpaid caring responsibilities. These women are also offered occupational segregation. The work of women is generally undervalued and there has been notable pay discrimination across the UK. These all factors contribute to the inequality of gender in the UK.

5.4. Influence of gender inequality on social development and progress

Gender inequality is widely linked with a negative influence on social development and progress. The influence of gender inequality is increasingly ambiguous and can be a notable hindrance to growth. The income and the wages are steadily influenced and can modify the aggregate demand (Bilan et al. 2020). As per Heise et al. (2019), these differences in income and wages can regulate the system of incentives that plan the investment across the human capital that in return also impact growth. On the other hand, the gender gap across education has an unfavourable influence on growth because of the large externalities that are generated through improved parental dissemination and female education. In health and life, gender inequality can impede long-term growth because of the lowered working lives and productivity levels. These influences are the barriers that are developed by gender inequality and posed threat to social development (Lundberg and Stearns, 2019). On the other hand, concerning social development, gender inequality is considered to be increasingly harmful. The reason is that the quality generally promotes educational outcomes alongside societal health. Therefore, working on the issue of gender is increasingly important as in the UK gender inequality is viewed as one of the most severe inequalities (Heise et al. 2019).

6. Discussion

The findings of the study have shown that gender equity and the achievement of goals including profitable and social rights, health, and education are always together (Eastin, 2018). Gender equality is viewed as a matter of social justice which allows equal rights to use resources, rights, and opportunities. Thus, the leadership precisely the women's leadership is dynamic for all levels as it carries a change in equality of gender. Consequently, the women leader might not be noticeable still when the exertions are made including practices at the community level. The leader needs to have a clear idea for changing the country. This is precisely significant regarding gender issues as the conversion is just likely by engaging with a wide range of stakeholders including men and women. Therefore, it is important to adopt such a method which is a key to gender equality (Breda et al. 2020). Furthermore, it has also been found that numerous features subsidize gender inequality in the setting of the UK. For instance, amongst numerous factors few of the prominent factors due to which the UK has not accomplished gender equality are stereotyping, prejudice, and other social norms (Zamberlan et al. 2022). It is usually observed that gender discrimination transversely in the workplace is unlawful in the UK for the past few decades.

Gender inequality is extensively connected with a negative impact on social growth and development. The effect of gender inequality is progressively vague and can be a prominent burden on growth. The income and

the wages are steadily influenced and can adjust the collective demand (Bilan et al. 2020). As per Heise et al. (2019), these differences in income and wages can regulate the system of incentives that plan the investment across the human capital that in return also impact growth. Further mainly, it is observed that the decrease in the gender gaps mainly in education led in the direction of economic pay-off. Hence, addressing gender inequalities can largely promote economic growth. Though, the indication from the study of Falk and Hermle (2018), showed how the interference can develop economic empowerment which has endorsed education, revenue, and individual wellbeing. The findings also indicated that Bhattacharya (2022) added that the significance of custom and culture and the essence of engaging with direct and cultural norms provision the human right for the accomplishment of positive renovation across gender equality. Accordingly, the objectives of gender quality can be expressed in echo alongside the local communities. On the other hand, concerning social development gender inequality is considered to be increasingly harmful. The reason is that the quality generally promotes educational outcomes alongside societal health (Heise et al. 2019). Therefore, working on the issue of gender is increasingly important as in the UK gender inequality is viewed as one of the most severe inequalities.

7. Conclusion and Future Implications

In conclusion, most gender inequalities are persistent in the economy. Gender is regarded as one of the prominent deliberations for development. It is observed as the way in which the power structure and the social norms affect the opportunities accessible to different groups of women and men. Gender equality is significant in its own right while development is the procedure for expanding freedom across all the people. It thereby closes the gap among the genders i.e., males and females as they play part in lowering income and poverty. Gender is one of the significant considerations for development. Gender stereotypes influence study choices, behaviour, and attitude regarding the association. The promotion of gender equality through targeted programs and policies can imply economic growth and gender equality simultaneously. This in return can improve the argument for public investment in gender equality. The reason is that some private companies largely promote gender equality based on profitability. For future researchers, it has been recommended that the research needs to be focused on the specific views and opinions of the respondents. This means that future researchers can collect information by using primary sources. In addition, the research can be further focused on a specific theory of gender equality and social development whereas other kinds of development such as economic and cultural developments can also be considered when conducting the study.

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